

LINGUOPRAGMATIC ANALYSIS OF A LITERARY TEXT: THE EXPRESSION OF CONTEXT AND AUTHOR'S INTENTION

N.Z. Nasrullaeva¹, D. Giasova², N. Boymurodova³

Professor of Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages¹

Teacher of Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages²

Student of Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages³

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15333856>

Abstract. *This article is devoted to the study of the linguopragmatic analysis of a literary text, the methods of expressing context and author's intention. The article analyzes in detail the concept of context, its types and its role in the formation of meaning in a literary text. Linguopragmatic and discursive methodological approaches are described to determine the author's intention. Practical analyses are presented on the example of major examples of Uzbek literature, revealing pragmatic strategies in a literary text. According to the results of the study, linguopragmatic analysis is an important tool for identifying hidden ideas in literary works and conveying them to the modern reader.*

Keywords: *fictional text, linguopragmatics, context, author's intention, discourse, semantic-pragmatic analysis, Uzbek literature, communicative strategies, inference, aesthetic interpretation.*

Introduction. A literary text is a reflection of human thought and the spiritual world. Literary works are created through language and become a means of conveying aesthetic, moral, social, and political ideas to the reader. Language serves not only to express thought, but also as a means of giving it meaning in a certain context and controlling the reader's perception. It is at this point that the relevance of the linguopragmatic approach emerges.

Linguopragmatics analyzes speech acts expressed in language, how they are understood in context, and the intentions of the speaker (author). In the analysis of a literary text, the linguopragmatic method makes it possible to study the hidden or explicit goals of the author, how they are expressed using context and language tools.

This article discusses in detail the need for linguopragmatic analysis of a literary text, the relationship between context and author's intention, and how they are expressed in the text. Practical analyses are also presented based on examples from Uzbek literature.

I. Linguopragmatics and literary text: theoretical foundations

1.1. The concept and tasks of linguopragmatics

Linguopragmatics is a field that analyzes speech activity, that is, the practical use of language tools, based on purpose and context. Its main task is to determine the meaning of a speech act, its hidden intentions, and the speaker's goal.

Charles Morris (1938) divided linguistic research into syntactic, semantic, and pragmatic aspects. Pragmatics, according to his definition, deals with the relationship of signs to the user. Later, this direction was developed by scientists such as Austin, Searle, and Grice, creating the theory of speech acts.

Literature Review and methodology. A number of important studies have been conducted by world and Uzbek scholars in the field of linguopragmatic analysis of literary texts. In Uzbek linguistics, F. Karimov (2017) studied the interrelationship of linguopragmatics and speech activity and determined the linguistic foundations of literary text analysis. A. Rajabov (2018) deeply studied the linguistic features of discourse analysis, and A. Kochkarov (2016) deeply studied text pragmatics and its methodological foundations. From the examples of literary works, the works of Abdulla Qodiriy, Chulpon, and Otkir Hoshimov were studied as practical examples of linguopragmatic approaches to the transmission of social, cultural, and philosophical ideas through literary texts. This literary heritage has created classic examples of the transmission of hidden meanings through artistic language and means of aesthetic expression. Thus, the existing literature serves as a theoretical and practical basis for the formation of methods of linguopragmatic and discursive analysis of literary texts.

Analysis of a literary text from a linguopragmatic point of view requires studying not only the form and content of language units, but also their communicative and expressive significance.

The literary text and its communicative nature

The literary text is a two-way communicative process:

- On the one hand, the author seeks to convey his intention to the reader through the text.
- On the other hand, the reader interprets the text based on his knowledge, experience and context.

A literary text is not just a description of events, but also a complex system of socio-cultural codes, aesthetic norms, and personal worldviews. For this reason, a linguopragmatic approach plays an important role in the analysis of a literary text.

Context and its significance in a literary text. The concept and types of context. Context is a set of external and internal conditions necessary for determining and fully understanding the meaning of a particular language unit. In a literary text, context is closely related to the relationships between parts of the text, the ideas expressed by the author in the socio-cultural background, and the reader's knowledge base.

In linguistic studies, context is usually divided into:

- Extralinguistic (specialized) context - historical, political, cultural situations, the existing environment in society.
- Linguistic context - relationships with other words and sentences in the text.
- Situational context - a real or imagined speech situation.

Extralinguistic context is very important for fully understanding a literary text. For example, Abdulla Qodiriy wrote the novel "Bygone Days" in the conditions of 1920s Uzbekistan, and he expressed the socio-political problems of his time and the need for reforms through artistic images. To fully understand this work, it is necessary to know the context of that period.

Linguistic context is determined by the interconnection of words and sentences in the text. For example, artistic devices such as metaphor and irony are often revealed through linguistic context.

Situational context is important in understanding the communication of characters, their circumstances and moods. This is very clearly manifested in dialogues.

Formation of meaning through context In a literary text, many meanings are transmitted not directly, but through context.

Even if the text appears to be a simple story on the surface, it can actually contain deep meanings. For example, in Cholpon's poems, the words "flower" and "spring" are often used as symbols of freedom and renewal. To understand these meanings, it is necessary to know the social situation during the colonial period when the poems were written.

In Otkir Hoshimov's "The Works of the World", deep philosophical conclusions are hidden behind ordinary everyday events. The author, describing ordinary life situations, encourages the reader to think about human values. Thus, the context helps not only to reveal the meaning of the text, but also to understand the author's hidden intentions.

Author's intention and its expression. The concept of authorial intent and its components.

Authorial intent is the main goals and ideas that the creator of a literary text wants to convey to the reader through his work. The author seeks to express his inner world and views on life through each image, image, dialogue, metaphor.

The main components of the authorial intent:

- Spiritual and moral idea - reflection of ideas about society, man and life.
- Aesthetic ideal - image of beauty, spiritual purity and human values.
- Socio-political position - attitude to certain modern problems, social injustices.
- Emotional-affectiveness - encouraging the reader to think by influencing his feelings.

Methods for analyzing the author's intention

The following methods are used to analyze the author's intention:

- Pragmatic inference - identifying information that is not directly expressed, based on the text and context.
- Discursive analysis - studying the text within the framework of the social, cultural and historical context.
- Semantic-pragmatic analysis - identifying the semantic and pragmatic properties of language units.

For example, in the works of Charles S. Peirce and Herbert Paul Grice, methods for identifying hidden meanings through pragmatic inference were developed. Grice's theory of "implicature" emphasizes the need for the reader to understand incompletely expressed meanings in the text using context.

Expression of the author's intention through artistic means

The author uses various artistic means to express his intention:

- Metaphor and metonymy - figurative expression of complex feelings and concepts.
- Symbolism - conveying abstract ideas to the reader through special designations.
- Dialogue and monologue - revealing ideas through the dialogue of characters.
- Contrast and opposition - strengthening one's idea through comparison.

Literary example: Abdulla Qodiriy in "Bygone Days" shows the struggle between renewal and oldness in society through the images of Otabek and Komiljon. Through the image of Otabek, the author advocates innovation, promotes the idea of justice and progress.

Another example: In Cholpon's novel "Night and Day", the ideas of national liberation, justice and human freedom are expressed through the struggle of the heroes. Here the author's intention is shown at the same time on a social and personal level.

Results and discussion. Thus, in order to correctly understand the author's intention, it is not enough to just read the text, but to analyze it in depth, study the context, artistic means and communicative strategies.

Linguopragmatic analysis of a literary text: methodological approaches and practical examples. Stages of literary text analysis.

The following main stages are followed for the analysis of a literary text using the linguopragmatic method:

1. General study of the text - analysis of the event and plot, identification of characters and main ideas.

2. Identification of language means - analysis of the use of artistic techniques such as metaphor, irony, symbol, contrast.

3. Study of the context - study of the period, social conditions and cultural context in which the text was created.

4. Analysis of the author's intention - identification of hidden or explicit goals in the text.

5. Taking into account the reader's interpretation - analysis of how the text is perceived by different readers.

Pragmatic inference and contextual analysis methods are widely used at each stage.

Linguopragmatic strategies. It is very important to identify the linguopragmatic strategies used by the author when analyzing a literary text. They include the following:

- Dialogical strategy - conveying hidden meanings through dialogue between characters.
- Monological strategy - addressing the reader by expressing the character's inner experiences.
- Symbolic strategy - conveying deep meanings through symbols.
- Ironic and sarcastic strategy - expressing criticism and ideas indirectly, rather than directly.

With the help of these strategies, the author not only clearly states his intention, but also enhances it on an aesthetic level.

Practical analysis: examples from Uzbek literature

Let's now do a linguopragmatic analysis based on several practical examples from Uzbek literature:

Example: Abdulla Qodiriy – “Bygone Days”

- Context: The work was written during the period of increasing Jadidism and colonialism in the Turkestan region.
- Author's intention: To show the struggle between old-fashionedness and renewal in society.
- Linguopragmatic analysis:
 - The image of Otabek is used as a symbol of innovation, progress, and justice.
 - The author presents Otabek's actions as an ideal and criticizes the old-fashioned worldview (the image of Komiljon).
 - The dialogues express the difference between the demands of the time and human values.

Conclusion. Linguopragmatic analysis of a literary text is not only an understanding of the content of a literary work, but also a process of fully understanding the author's inner world, attitude to society and life, aesthetic and moral values. As we have considered in this article:

- Linguopragmatics studies how language means convey meaning, how they affect the reader.
- Context is the main factor necessary for the correct understanding of the meaning of a literary text. Linguistic, situational and extralinguistic contexts shape the content of the text and allow the reader to understand it in depth.
- The author's intention can be expressed hidden in the deep layers of the text, and its detection is carried out through pragmatic analysis.
- Pragmatic inference, discursive and semantic-pragmatic methods play an important role in the analysis of a literary text.
- In the examples of Uzbek literature (A. Qodiriy, Cholpon, O. Hoshimov), literary texts used deep linguopragmatic tools to express the problems of their time, human values, and changes in society.

In conclusion, the analysis of a literary text from a linguopragmatic and discursive perspective serves not only to provide a deeper understanding of the literary work, but also to strengthen the aesthetic-cultural dialogue between the author and the reader. This creates the basis for new scientific research in literary studies and linguistics.

REFERENCES

1. Morris, C. (1938). *Foundations of the Theory of Signs*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press. — 121 p.
2. Austin, J. L. (1962). *How to Do Things with Words*. Oxford: Clarendon Press. — 150 p.
3. Searle, J. R. (1969). *Speech Acts: An Essay in the Philosophy of Language*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. — 203 p.
4. Grice, H. P. (1975). *Logic and Conversation*. In P. Cole & J. Morgan (Eds.), *Syntax and Semantics*, vol. 3, *Speech Acts*. New York: Academic Press. — 65-75 p.
5. Karimov, F. (2017). *Speech Activity and Linguopragmatics*. Tashkent: National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan Publishing House. — 230 p.
6. Rajabov, A. (2018). *Discourse and its Linguistic Analysis*. Tashkent: Science and Technology Publishing House. — 198 p.
7. Kuchkarov, A. (2016). *Fundamentals of Textual Pragmatics*. Tashkent: Ma'naviyat. — 210 p.
8. Qodiriy, A. (1992). *Days Gone*. Tashkent: Gafur Ghulam Publishing House of Literature and Art. — 320 p.
9. Cholpon. (1991). *Night and Day*. Tashkent: Gafur Ghulam Publishing House of Literature and Art. — 288 p.
10. Hoshimov, O. (2015). *Works of the World*. Tashkent: Yangi asr avlod. — 416 p.